

**CONNECTING
WOMEN
IN DIGITAL**

OVERVIEW OF NATIONAL ACTIONS

WP2, Task 2.1

VT

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ABSTRACT

This report presents an overview of the current landscape of Women in Digital (WiD) initiatives across Europe, aiming to assess the visibility, focus, and distribution of actions dedicated to increasing women's participation and leadership in the digital sector.

To ensure a robust and data-driven perspective, the study employs a multi-source methodology. First, operational initiatives were collected through targeted online research, focusing exclusively on programs that directly target girls or women with digital training, events, or mentorship. Second, the report analyses national-level allocations of EU Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and Cohesion Fund resources, identifying financial commitments to gender equality in the context of digital transformation. Using normalized indicators across four criteria – presence of operational initiatives, proportion of RRF and Cohesion funding dedicated to gender equality, and the share of Cohesion projects specifically focused on the WiD topic – each Member State is ranked to assess its overall activity and visibility in this space.

Leadership-oriented initiatives remain the most underrepresented phase, signalling a gap in enabling women to rise to decision-making roles in tech and digital sectors. Additionally, most European initiatives lack an intersectional lens, often failing to address overlapping barriers related to ethnicity, migration status, sexual orientation, disability or socioeconomic background. In contrast, global or non-European programs more frequently embed these intersecting dimensions into their design and implementation. The results show wide disparities across Member States. While countries like Austria, Germany, and Sweden demonstrate leadership through strong funding and initiative presence. Nearly 40% of Member States exhibit little to no national-level activity.

The list of WiD operational initiatives and the list of Cohesion Fund WiD related projects are added as annexes in this report.

KEYWORDS

Women in Digital, operational initiatives, gender balance, EU funding.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable presents an analysis of existing initiatives, funding mechanisms, related to gender balance and Women in Digital (WiD) landscape. Grounded in the framework of the “leaky pipeline”, which illustrates the progressive decline of women’s participation across the digital career path, the report reveals key insights and disparities across Member States (MS) and programmatic phases.

The report indicates that the majority of initiatives are concentrated in the ICT and Digital employment phases, while STEM-focused initiatives are often localized or integrated into school curricula. Leadership-oriented initiatives are notably scarce, exposing a critical gap in efforts to support women’s progression into decision-making and executive roles in the digital sector.

Germany, Austria, and Sweden emerge as frontrunners based on normalized scoring of four indicators: presence of operational initiatives, share of RRF and Cohesion funding allocated to gender equality, and number of WiD-related projects. In stark contrast, 11 Member States have no visible national-level initiatives, highlighting significant regional disparities.

Only 3.4% of the €655 billion distributed through the EU’s Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) is dedicated to gender equality, with further variation in Cohesion Fund allocations. Notably, Austria leads in Cohesion Fund use for WiD-related initiatives, while Sweden allocates the highest proportion of RRF funds to gender equality (19%).

While many non-European initiatives tend to adopt an intersectional lens, incorporating considerations of race, language, religion, migration status, and socio-economic background, most European WiD programs remain narrowly focused on gender dimension alone. This limited scope overlooks the compounded barriers faced by

women from marginalized or underrepresented communities, including those with diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Addressing these intersecting inequalities is important for building a more inclusive and effective digital policy landscape across Europe.

A composite index ranking countries based on four normalized metrics places Austria, Germany, and Sweden in the top three positions, respectively. At the lower end of the ranking are Denmark, Luxembourg, and Malta. However, it is important to note that these results reflect only the visibility of Women in Digital (WiD) initiatives, specifically in terms of operational programs and national funding and do not necessarily represent the broader landscape of gender equality or the lived experiences of women in the digital sector within each country. To gain a fuller understanding of the current state of WiD across Member States, upcoming Connect Women in Digital (WIDCON) project activities will focus on both primary and secondary data collection, complemented by WiD Forum engagements and Summits. These efforts aim to support the development of more inclusive digital ecosystems.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction.....	11
1.1. Purpose of the deliverable.....	11
1.2. Scope of the deliverable	12
2. Initiative search results and insights.....	15
2.1. Insights from the operational initiatives targeting Women in Digital	15
2.1.1. Initiative distribution, based on targeted audience, phase	16
2.1.2. National initiatives	21
2.2. Insights on EU funding distribution for women in digital initiatives	24
2.2.1. Resilience and recovery funding	24
2.2.2. Cohesion funding	30
2.3. Results of women in digital initiative popularity estimation	42
3. Methodology of initiative search and mapping	46
3.1. Identification of possible data sources	47
3.2. Search and mapping of operational initiatives targeting Women in Digital	51
3.3. Automated gathering of initiative funding data	53
3.4. ML model building.....	54
4. Discussion	61
4.1. Conclusions	61
4.2. Future work.....	63
5. Annex I. Initial list of operational initiatives targeting Women in Digital topic	65
6. Annex II. List of WiD related projects among Cohesion Funds.....	73

LIST OF FIGURES

Fig. 1 Leaky pipeline of Women in Digital.....	13
Fig. 2 Summary of WiD operating initiatives in different geographical regions and oriented phases.....	16
Fig. 3 Summary of WiD operating initiatives distribution in Europe.....	18
Fig. 4 Summary of national level WiD operating initiatives distribution by country	22
Fig. 5 Summary on what amount was granted to each MS (right) and what amount was contributing to gender equality	26
Fig. 6 Proportion of RRF funds in each MS, dedicated to gender equality	27
Fig. 7 RRF amount, dedicated to gender equality distribution based on measurement type and social category	27
Fig. 8 RRF amount, dedicated to gender equality distribution by Social Category from the Equality thematic	28
Fig. 9 Yearly Cohesion Fund amounts, dedicated to gender equality and WiD related topic.....	32
Fig. 10 Cohesion Fund amounts in each country (a), dedicated to gender equality category (b) and WiD related topic (c).....	33
Fig. 11 Proportion of Cohesion Fund, dedicated to gender equality category in each country	34
Fig. 12 Proportion of Cohesion Fund, dedicated to gender equality category in each country	34
Fig. 13 WiD related projects distribution among different categories of intervention	35

Fig. 14 Proportion of WiD related projects among all Cohesion Fund projects in terms of amount and projects 36

Fig. 15 Average project budget for Cohesion Fund projects and specifically WiD related projects in each country..... 37

Fig. 16 Proportion of Cohesion Fund, dedicated to WiD related projects in each country 38

Fig. 17 General schema of WiD initiative data collection and analysis..... 46

Fig. 18 Example dashboard of RRF data in Qlik Sense Hub platform, selected to reflect funding for gender equality 49

Fig. 19 Word clouds from WiD operational initiative web page texts (a) and from web age text from similar initiatives (b) 55

Fig. 20 Unique word clouds from WiD operational initiative web page texts (a) and from web age text from similar initiatives (b) 55

Fig. 21 Confusion matrixes for WiD prediction for overall (a) and for false-positive (b) oriented cases 57

Fig. 22 Ratios of records after the filtering and manual revision 59

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. List of EU MS and normalized values of their performance in different aspects of WiD initiatives 43

Table 2. List of initiatives on Women in Digital 65

Table 2. List of projects on Women in Digital..... 73

GLOSSARY

Cohesion	European Union (EU) financial instrument designed to reduce economic and social disparities and promote sustainable development across EU member states.
DIGITAL	Phase in a leady pipeline, defining initiatives focus on entry-level employment, workplace retention, reskilling and career progression support mechanisms
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology. Phase in a leady pipeline, defining policies and programs that support women in choosing and succeeding in tertiary education focused on digital and technical disciplines.
Leadership	Phase in a leady pipeline, defining mentorship programs, board diversity strategies, and leadership development training.
ML	Machine learning
MS	Member states
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics. Phase in a leady pipeline, defining initiatives aimed at early exposure, interest-building, and reducing gender stereotypes in technical subjects.
WiD	Women in Digital
WIDCON	"Connecting Women in Digital" consortium under EC grant agreement 101195389
Operational initiative	Initiatives, that are visible in the internet and invites girls or women to join it, use its benefits, advancing in digital sector, not taking into account its formal status or funding source.
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility, one of the European Union's largest financial instruments created in response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

1. Introduction

The digital transformation of our societies and economies presents a unique opportunity to foster inclusive growth and equitable innovation across Europe. Yet, despite the growing reliance on digital technologies, women remain significantly underrepresented in digital professions, education, and leadership roles. In response, the European Commission and EU Member States have endorsed the Women in Digital (WiD) Declaration¹, a commitment to closing the gender gap in the digital sector through coordinated policy efforts and strategic initiatives. The European Commission Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025² and Roadmap for Women's Rights³ indicate a strong institutional commitment to gender equality and women's empowerment. However, current initiatives remain fragmented and a comprehensive vision of existing women in digital efforts is still lacking.

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable

This report aims to shed light on the breadth of existing women in digital initiatives across Europe, offering a structured and summarized view of actions by Member States.

It presents a comprehensive catalogue of initiatives that contribute to the objectives of the WiD Declaration. By mapping and analysing these efforts, the report highlights the visibility of existing programs, identifying best practices, gaps, and opportunities for stronger policy coherence and greater impact. This summary is an important step

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=58562

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0152>

³ https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/0c3fe55d-9e4f-4377-9d14-93d03398b434_en?filename=Gender%20Equality%20Report%20Chapeau%20Communication.pdf

toward ensuring that gender equality is embedded across Europe’s digital landscape, not only as a matter of social justice, but as a driver of innovation, competitiveness, and sustainability.

The findings are relevant in the context of Europe’s Digital Decade and its 2030 targets⁴, which aims to empower citizens, businesses, and public administrations through digital transformation. Achieving the Digital Decade’s vision of a digitally sovereign, inclusive, and resilient Europe is inseparable from the active participation of women in shaping and leading the digital future. This report, therefore, serves not only as a reflection of current efforts but also as a strategic tool to support evidence-based policymaking, and ensure that the digital decade is inclusive for all who are willing to follow the available possibilities.

1.2. Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable focuses on identifying and summarizing existing initiatives across Europe that support women's participation and advancement in the digital sector. Initiatives, which identify girls, women as the primary target audience in digital sectors are included. Gender-neutral programs, those targeting all genders but only reporting the proportion of women reached were excluded. This decision is based on the recognition that equal methods do not necessarily yield equitable outcomes due to systemic gendered disparities, reinforcing the need for women- and girl-centered approaches. The analysis is framed using the “leaky pipeline” model (see Fig. 1), which illustrates the progressive decline in women’s representation at key stages of the digital

⁴https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/europes-digital-decade-digital-targets-2030_en

career path. This conceptual tool helps pinpoint where interventions are most urgently needed.

Fig. 1 Leaky pipeline of Women in Digital

Source: Created by the authors.

To structure this analysis, the pipeline has been divided into four key phases, which will be used to structure the initiatives in this deliverable as well:

- STEM – Encouraging girls’ participation in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) subjects from primary to secondary education. This phase includes initiatives aimed at early exposure and interest-building in technical subjects, with a focus on challenging gender stereotypes that limit participation.
- ICT – Increasing women’s participation in higher education and vocational training in ICT-related fields. This phase covers policies and programs that

support women in choosing and succeeding in tertiary education focused on digital and technical disciplines.

- **DIGITAL** – Supporting the transition of women from ICT or non-ICT education into the digital workforce and helping them remain in technical or digital roles during their early careers. Initiatives here focus on entry-level employment, workplace retention, reskilling and career progression support mechanisms.
- **LEADERSHIP** – Enabling and empowering women to attain leadership positions within the digital sector, whether in private companies, public institutions, or entrepreneurial ventures. This includes mentorship programs, board diversity strategies, and leadership development training.

The scope of this deliverable is limited to identifying and categorizing initiatives based on their alignment with one or more of these four pipeline phases. While the report captures the presence and thematic focus of these initiatives, it does not attempt to evaluate the internal design, effectiveness, or measurable impact of each program. Such detailed assessment falls outside the scope of this content and would require a deeper, evaluation-driven methodology.

Where possible, initiatives are linked to their geographic coverage at the national or regional level. This geographic mapping supports a clearer, policy-relevant overview of how different countries are addressing the various stages of the pipeline. It also lays a foundation for future analysis, enabling stakeholders to identify strengths, gaps, and opportunities for cross-national collaboration and enhancement of women's roles in the digital decade.

2. Initiative search results and insights

This section presents a targeted search of existing initiatives across Europe that directly engage and support women in digital. In line with gender mainstreaming principles, this deliverable distinguishes between general-purpose programs and those designed specifically for women. While many digital education, training, and mentoring initiatives claim to be gender-neutral, they often unconsciously cater to male audiences, both in structure and delivery. As a result, women face barriers to full participation and benefit.

To address this, the scope of this analysis includes only those initiatives that explicitly target girls/women, whether through tailored outreach, specialized content, or dedicated support mechanisms. General inclusion programs aimed at all genders are excluded unless they have a clearly defined and intentional component focused on overcoming the specific barriers faced by girls/women in STEM, ICT, digital careers, and leadership. This focus ensures that the obtained lists highlight actions that genuinely address the “leaky pipeline” of women in digital, rather than assuming equal benefit from universal approaches.

2.1. Insights from the operational initiatives targeting Women in Digital

Operational initiatives are defined as programs visible online that invite girls or women to participate and benefit from offerings such as training, events, mentorship, or role models. The classification is independent of the organization’s type (NGO, SME, association, etc.) and depends solely on whether the initiative provides tangible support explicitly for women and girls in digital fields. Therefore, the search of initiatives was conducted online, focusing on programs that explicitly invite girls and women to participate or make use of shared resources and materials.

2.1.1. Initiative distribution, based on targeted audience, phase

This section presents the distribution of existing initiatives according to the four phases of the WiD “leaky pipeline” (see Annex I): STEM, ICT, Digital, and Leadership. Close to European initiatives (available in one or several EU countries), non-European were listed, as well as global ones, which are active in multiple continents, including Europe (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Summary of WiD operating initiatives in different geographical regions and oriented phases

Source: Created by the authors.

While there is a noticeable concentration of programs aimed at advancing women's skills in STEM, ICT, and Digital technologies, Leadership is an area that remains significantly underrepresented across the initiatives. This may reflect not only a perceived lower demand for leadership training compared to general workforce development but also the dominance of generic leadership programs that are not

tailored to the digital sector⁵ (and thus fall outside the scope of this deliverable). Additionally, persistent gender biases that question women's suitability for leadership roles particularly in technical fields may further contribute to the lack of targeted leadership initiatives⁶.

Although it might be expected that the number of initiatives supporting women in digital would decrease across the four phases—mirroring the declining participation of women—the data shows otherwise. In fact, the number of initiatives does not follow this downward trend. This discrepancy is largely due to the nature of STEM-related programs, which are often local in scope, less visible at the national level, and sometimes embedded within school curricula. As a result, the majority of initiatives are concentrated in the ICT and digital phases, where the focus is on preparing women for employment. These programs aim to enhance digital literacy and promote the integration of digital technologies into both everyday life and professional environments. Such initiatives are essential for equipping women with the skills needed to thrive in a technology-driven world.

An analysis of how initiatives available in Europe are distributed across the different phases of the Women in Digital pipeline in a global context (see Fig. 3) reveals that all phases except for Leadership are primarily represented at the national level, with individual countries leading the activities. In contrast, the Leadership phase shows a smaller proportion of nationally led initiatives and a greater presence of regional

⁵ Emma, L. (2024). Skill-Building Initiatives to Foster Women's Leadership in STEM and Emerging Industries.

⁶ Ramseook-Munhurrin, P., Naidoo, P., & Armoogum, S. (2025). Navigating the challenges of female leadership in the information and communication technology and engineering sectors. *Journal of Business and Socio-economic Development*, 5(1), 55-70.

(involving at least two European countries) or global programs (not affiliated with a single country or active across multiple continents). This trend may reflect the growing recognition of leadership as an area of international relevance, requiring cross-border collaboration and visibility beyond local or national efforts.

Fig. 3 Summary of WiD operating initiatives distribution in Europe

Source: Created by the authors.

Leadership training emerges as the most significant gap across the collected data. Although some programs like DevelopHer⁷ and Female Tech leaders⁸ include leadership components, most of initiatives focus primarily on technical training without addressing the critical leadership skills needed for women to advance into decision-making positions. This gap is particularly significant, as leadership remains one of the key barriers to achieving equitable representation in the tech and digital sectors.

⁷ <https://developer.org/>

⁸ <https://www.femaletechleaders.com/>

Without targeted support for leadership development, women may struggle to break through the glass ceiling despite excelling in technical skills.

STEM, ICT and DIGITAL phase-oriented initiatives are similarly represented at the national level, with approximately 50% being locally implemented in a single European country. However, as the phases progress, there is a noticeable increase in the proportion of initiatives operating at global level, rather than being limited to Europe. Individual initiatives often address multiple phases of the Women in Digital pipeline, typically covering one to two areas. There is no significant statistical difference in this pattern across national, European, or global initiatives. Notably, only one initiative (ECWT – the European Centre for Women in Technology), targets all four phases.

“ECWT serves as a European single point of contact for information gathering, collection and analysis of data, research, and the development of appropriate methodological tools aimed at increasing the participation of girls in STEM, supporting the retention and advancement of women in the digital economy, promoting women’s contribution to ICT innovation, and fostering women entrepreneurship in tech. In addition, ECWT actively supports female-led ICT start-ups and consolidates one of the largest networks dedicated to closing the Digital Gender Gap in Europe.”⁹ . By serving as central platform, ECWT brings together a broad range of stakeholders to strengthen efforts across the Women in Digital landscape

Programs that integrate all four phases of the digital pipeline STEM, ICT, Digital, and Leadership offer a more comprehensive approach to advancing gender equity in the digital age. Initiatives like ECWT provide valuable structural pathways for participation;

⁹ <https://ecwt.eu/about-us/>

however, there is a need for additional programs that allow women in all their diversity to explore different roles and trajectories within digital sectors. Such holistic initiatives should not only provide robust technical training but also intentionally build the leadership capacities necessary for women to thrive in decision-making positions.

Importantly, data analysis revealed a notable difference in how inclusivity is conceptualized geographically. European initiatives that focus on Women in Digital tend to apply a singular gender lens, primarily targeting women and girls without further differentiation. In contrast, non-European initiatives particularly in the United States and parts of the global South tend to adopt more intersectional approaches. These initiatives often target specific subgroups, such as Black girls and women, Muslim girls, or LGBTQ+ youth, recognizing that gender does not operate in isolation from race, religion, sexual orientation, or socioeconomic status. Such efforts acknowledge that advancing digital inclusion requires addressing the unique and compounded barriers that arise at the intersection of multiple identities.

This contrast underscores the need for European initiatives to broaden their frameworks to better reflect intersectional realities. Current efforts, while valuable, may fall short in reaching girls and women who face structural disadvantages beyond gender alone. Recognizing and responding to these intersecting inequalities such as those shaped by migration status, ethnicity, disability, socio-economic status or geography can help ensure that digital empowerment strategies are more effective.

The overall trend indicates that while technical skills are being prioritized, there is an increasing need for initiatives to also cultivate leadership capabilities in women. By combining technical proficiency with the confidence and skills needed for leadership, these programs can ensure that women not only enter the digital workforce but are also empowered to take on positions of influence and authority.

In sum, closing the digital gender gap requires more than equal access to technology or training. It calls for a systemic shift that recognizes diversity within gender, prioritizes inclusive leadership development, and foregrounds intersectional barriers that limit participation and advancement. Leadership training, in particular, holds potential not just for individual empowerment, but for reshaping digital spaces to be more equitable and representative of the societies they serve. While intersectionality is not yet clearly reflected in many existing European initiatives, acknowledging and integrating it represents a critical path forward. Doing so would help address not only gender-based disparities but also the broader, interrelated forms of exclusion shaped by race, class, disability, migration status, and other social factors.

2.1.2. National initiatives

The analysis of the Women in Digital initiatives at the national level covered 27 European countries, with the USA included as a comparative reference point. The data reveals significant disparities in engagement and activity levels across countries. In total, 65 initiatives were identified across the 27 European countries, resulting in an average of just two-three initiatives per country (2,41). However, this average conceals considerable variation: the median number of initiatives is only one, indicating that in most countries, activity in this area remains limited. Notably, the United States stands out with eight initiatives, followed closely by Germany and Great Britain with seven, positioning them as the most active in promoting women's inclusion in the digital space (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Summary of national level WiD operating initiatives distribution by country

Source: Created by the authors.

A substantial number of countries (ten in total) have no recorded Women in Digital initiatives. These include Austria, Cyprus, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Luxembourg, Slovakia, and Slovenia. This group accounts for nearly 40% of the countries in the dataset, raising concerns about the uneven prioritization of gender equality in the digital innovation landscape. Additionally, five countries, including Bulgaria, Greece, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden, have taken minimal steps, with just one initiative each.

On the more active end of the spectrum, countries like Spain, Italy (with six initiatives), Belgium, Ireland, Lithuania, and Romania (with five initiatives), reflecting a stronger commitment to fostering women participation in the digital economy. France, Hungary, Malta (with two initiatives), and Poland (with three initiatives) show moderate engagement. These patterns highlight a notable disparity across Europe – while some countries are actively fostering digital inclusion, others appear to be either falling

behind, lacking visibility for their efforts, or focusing their engagement at a broader international or global level.

When observing regional trends in the gathered data, Western European countries such as Germany, Belgium, and Ireland demonstrate moderate to high levels of activity, which may reflect more robust policy frameworks, greater public investment in digital inclusion, or more established gender equality structures. Southern European countries, including Spain, Italy, and Romania, show a surprisingly strong presence of initiatives, indicating growing awareness and proactive efforts to address digital gender disparities. Conversely, many Central and Eastern European countries show limited or no engagement, underscoring a potential gap in either capacity or prioritization of this issue.

This uneven distribution reveals both opportunities and challenges. The countries with the highest number of initiatives can serve as benchmarks, offering replicable strategies for fostering inclusive digital ecosystems. At the same time, the large number of countries with little to no recorded activity underscores the need for targeted support, capacity-building, and visibility. While pan-European and global initiatives can play a crucial role in bridging gaps, national-level Women in Digital programs are especially important. Locally grounded efforts are more likely to integrate intersectional perspectives and respond to the specific needs of women and girls, especially those at the intersections of multiple forms of marginalization such as race, ethnicity, socio-economic background, disability, or migration status. A national approach increases the potential for tailored digital inclusion strategies.

2.2. Insights on EU funding distribution for women in digital initiatives

Operational initiatives alone do not necessarily reflect a country's overall commitment to the Women in Digital agenda, as they may be implemented by a range of stakeholders and funded from diverse sources. To gain a clearer picture of national engagement, it is essential to analyse project-based funding, especially public investments allocated for gender equality in digital transformation. This helps estimate the scope and focus of each country's efforts and how actively they are addressing gender disparities in the digital domain.

2.2.1. Resilience and recovery funding

Within the broader framework of WiD, funding data from the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) offers critical insights into how Member States integrate gender equality into their digital transformation agendas. These figures reveal both the scale and intent of investments aligned with the EU's post-COVID recovery priorities, including social inclusion and digital transition. All funding data presented is derived from the official RRF platform, ensuring accuracy, transparency, and alignment with the European Commission's reporting standards.

By leveraging Qlik Sense Hub's interactive capabilities, we have developed a structured data framework to generate key analytical outputs. The data is analysed and presented in tailored dashboards that showcase the following fields:

- Total funding amounts per country.
- Funding amounts explicitly allocated to gender equality.

All the records are disaggregation by these data fields:

- Country.
- Social category.
- Measure.
- Type of measure.
- Thematic title.

These dashboards facilitate comparative analysis across MS and policy areas, allowing to monitor progress, identify gaps, and inform future strategic direction for advancing gender equality in digital transformation. Between 2021 and May 2025, a total of €655.6 billion was distributed through the Recovery and Resilience Facility. Of this, approximately €22 billion was explicitly allocated to measures contributing to gender equality. The amounts, distributed among each MS are presented in Fig. 5. In both total funding and gender equality-specific allocations, Italy received the largest share, followed by Spain. While all Member States benefit from RRF support, several including Croatia, Denmark, France, Luxembourg, and Malta did not allocate any of their RRF funding to gender equality measures. On average, only 3.4% of total RRF funds across the EU were directed toward gender equality, but national shares vary widely.

Fig. 5 Summary on what amount was granted to each MS (right) and what amount was contributing to gender equality

Source: Created by the authors.

As illustrated in Figure 6, Sweden stands out, dedicating 19% of its RRF funds to gender equality, the highest among all MS. Ireland follows with 9%, while Czechia, Italy, and Portugal each allocated approximately 6%. Slightly above the EU average are Cyprus, Finland, and Slovakia, each dedicating between 4–5%. In contrast, the majority of MS allocate significantly less or none at all to gender equality through the RRF. This uneven distribution highlights the need for stronger, more consistent integration of gender-responsive measures in national recovery plans.

Fig. 6 Proportion of RRF funds in each MS, dedicated to gender equality

Source: Created by the authors.

It is particularly insightful to examine how and where RRF funding for gender equality is allocated across MS (see Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 RRF amount, dedicated to gender equality distribution based on measurement type and social category

Source: Created by the authors.

Of the total earmarked amount for gender equality, 29% supports reforms (see red background area in Fig. 7) primarily in Employment and Skills, while the remaining 71% is directed toward investments (see blue and grey background areas in Fig. 7) mainly in Education and Childcare, Employment and Skills, Social Policies and not specified social category (grey background are in Fig. 7).

A key analytical point involves the distribution of gender equality-oriented funds across various social categories, specifically within the funding marked under the broader equality thematic (see Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 RRF amount, dedicated to gender equality distribution by Social Category from the Equality thematic

Source: Created by the authors.

This breakdown provides a more nuanced understanding of how gender equality is addressed in conjunction with other intersecting dimensions of inequality. In this slice,

Slovakia is leading with 44% of gender equality funding in Equality thematic for Health and Long-Term Care and 19% for Education and Childcare social categories. Ireland follows, allocating 37% to Employment and Skills and 12% to Education and Childcare. However, the majority of Member States dedicate less than 30% of their gender equality funding to the equality thematic, reflecting missed opportunities to address the full range of intersectional barriers women face.

Interestingly, Slovakia's allocations were exclusively focused on Social Policies category, despite it being the least commonly funded social category, with only 7 Member States investing in it. By contrast, the Employment and Skills category was the most popular, followed closely by Education and Childcare. These two categories are especially relevant to Women in Digital initiatives, as they address foundational aspects of digital access, upskilling, and workforce participation—areas where gender disparities are often most visible.

In conclusion, the analysis of RRF funding under the Women in Digital initiative highlights the uneven commitment of MS to advancing gender equality within the broader context of digital transformation. While a total of €21.9 billion, around 3.4% of all RRF funds, has been allocated to gender equality, the proportion and use of these funds differ significantly across countries. Tools like the Qlik Sense Hub dashboards enable transparent tracking and comparative insights, revealing leaders like Sweden and Ireland in gender-focused funding. Most of these investments are concentrated in Employment and Skills as well as Education and Childcare, reflecting close alignment with WiD priorities aimed at improving access, participation, and leadership opportunities for women in the digital sphere.

These findings underscore the importance of strategic fund allocation and continued monitoring to ensure impactful and inclusive digital transitions across the EU. However,

it is especially concerning that six EU Member States (over 20%) have not allocated any RRF funds toward gender equality. This raises critical questions about whether gender equality, particularly in digital transformation, is being sufficiently prioritized or recognized within national reform and investment agendas. The absence of dedicated funding suggests a need for further scrutiny and policy engagement to ensure no one is left behind in the digital shift, especially those at the intersections of multiple forms of marginalization.

2.2.2. Cohesion funding

Understanding how Cohesion Funds are allocated is crucial to assessing whether EU Member States are substantively committing resources to promote gender equality, particularly in the context of digital transformation. While the EU strongly encourages inclusive digital growth and gender-balanced development, funding priorities at the national and regional levels often vary. Without a clear examination of how Cohesion Funds are allocated, it is difficult to determine whether countries are actively addressing the underrepresentation of women in digital sectors or whether this critical issue is being overlooked. As the Cohesion Fund represents another significant source of national-level funding alongside RRF, it offers important insight into the practical implementation of gender-equality measures across the EU. To understand how countries prioritize (or neglect) the Women in Digital agenda through their use of Cohesion Funds spending, data from all funded projects as of May 2025¹⁰ was analysed. To assess the relevance of projects to gender equality in the digital sector, a two-stage evaluation process was applied. First, the category of intervention was used to identify operations potentially aligned with gender-focused objectives. Then,

¹⁰ <https://kohesio.ec.europa.eu/en/data/projects>

each project's title and summary (in English) was reviewed to assess its connection to WiD agenda, considering its stated goals, expected outcomes, and target groups. This allowed for the identification of projects that explicitly support gender inclusion and empowerment in digital transformation.

To contextualize the findings across EU Member States, the following project-level data was also considered:

- Country.
- Intervention start date.
- Intervention end date.
- Total eligible expenditure.
- EU contribution to the project.

There is a specific category of intervention “Equality between men and women in all areas, including in access to employment, career progression, reconciliation of work and private life and promotion of equal pay for equal work”. While this category is thematically aligned with the WiD agenda, not all operations within it are directly aimed at advancing the participation of women in digital fields. At the same time, several operations under other intervention categories may still be relevant to WiD goals, even if not explicitly framed under the gender equality label. To address this, a multi-stage filtering process both automated and manual was conducted, analysing project titles, summaries, stated aims, outcomes, and target groups (as presented in English). Through this process, 424 operations were identified as directly connected to the Women in Digital topic. These represent just 0.02% of all initiatives and associated funding, highlighting the limited visibility and prioritization of this area within the broader Cohesion Fund portfolio.

Since most projects include start and end dates, we were able to estimate temporal trends in funding for gender equality and WiD-related activities (see Fig. 9). For this analysis, it was assumed that funding is distributed evenly across each project's duration. Some inaccuracies may occur due to missing dates in certain project entries.

Fig. 9 Yearly Cohesion Fund amounts, dedicated to gender equality and WiD related topic

Source: Created by the authors.

The funding trend shows steady growth up until 2020, which aligns with the 2014–2020 programming period. A delay in project completion timelines is expected, as implementation and financial closure often extend beyond the official funding window.

When analysing the absolute amounts of funding dedicated to gender equality and WiD-related topics across countries, it is important to avoid interpreting the highest totals as indicators of leadership since overall funding levels are heavily influenced by country size and budget capacity. Nonetheless, these absolute figures can still offer valuable insights into broad geographical patterns of investment. The three maps below (see Fig. 10) illustrate the funding distribution among EU countries (part a), the amounts allocated to gender equality intervention category (part b) and the amounts dedicated

to projects related to WiD topic (part c). Interestingly, each map highlights a different country as the leading recipient in its respective area, suggesting that investment priorities vary considerably depending on how gender and digital inclusion are framed and operationalized at the national level.

Fig. 10 Cohesion Fund amounts in each country (a), dedicated to gender equality category (b) and WiD related topic (c)

Source: Created by the authors.

A clearer comparison of how Cohesion Funds are utilized for gender equality can be made by examining the percentage of total funds each country allocates to projects within the gender equality intervention category (see Fig. 11). It illustrates only 10 countries highlight this category, where Austria leads with 1.20% of the funding to this category, while the smallest non null amount reached just 0.01% (Lithuania case).

Fig. 11 Proportion of Cohesion Fund, dedicated to gender equality category in each country

Source: Created by the authors.

Another interesting perspective is how the EU and national funding was used. The 12th figure illustrates the proportions of EU versus country contributions within the gender equality category. Austria and Greece fund these projects entirely from national resources, without using EU budget allocations. Spain and Germany allocate up to 2% of their EU budget to gender equality projects, while other countries lean to higher EU support. Notably, Lithuania’s gender equality projects are fully funded by the EU budget.

Fig. 12 Proportion of Cohesion Fund, dedicated to gender equality category in each country

Source: Created by the authors.

As mentioned above, the WiD related project are not necessary categorized under gender equality. Figure 13 shows the distribution of intervention categories to which WiD-related projects have been assigned.

Fig. 13 WiD related projects distribution among different categories of intervention

Source: Created by the authors.

The size of each block represents the proportion of funding withing all WiD related projects. It illustrates that “Active inclusion, including with a view to promoting equal opportunities and active participation, and improving employability” and “Adaptation of workers, enterprises and entrepreneurs to change” are closely aligned with the category of to the “Equality between men and women in all areas, including in access to employment, career progression, reconciliation of work and private life and promotion of equal pay for equal work”. This alignment underscores Europe’s commitment to increasing the participation of women in the digital sector, aiming to boost women’s engagement in digital fields and contribute to the growth of the EU.

To better understand the use of Cohesion Funds for WiD-related projects, it is useful to examine both the proportion of the total funding amount and the share of projects dedicated to this topic (see Fig. 14).

Fig. 14 Proportion of WiD related projects among all Cohesion Fund projects in terms of amount and projects

Source: Created by the authors.

Austria is a leader among EU countries in term of proportion of projects, dedicated to WiD topic among all country funded projects. Specifically, 0.74% of Austria’s projects (28 out of 3775) are dedicated to women in digital topic, while from the budget perspective – it is just 0.19% of Austria budget for Cohesion Funded projects. In contrast, Finland dedicates the largest share of its Cohesion Fund budget to WiD projects, at 0.36%. This shows an interesting tendence, visible in figure 15 – Germany, Finland and Belgium dedicate bigger budgets for WiD related projects rather than in general Cohesion Fund projects. In case of Germany, the WiD related project average budget is more than twice bigger than in general Cohesion Fund project. While in

Slovakia, Slovenia and Romania, the WiD remated projects have up to 20% of standard Cohesion Fund budget in the country.

Fig. 15 Average project budget for Cohesion Fund projects and specifically WiD related projects in each country

Source: Created by the authors.

Analyzing the funding sources for WiD project budgets reveals that Austria and Slovenia do not utilize EU funds for these projects, relying entirely on national budgets (see Fig. 16). Germany dedicates 98% of its WiD project funding from national sources, Spain funds 91% domestically. Notably, no country allocates less than 15% of WiD project budgets from their national funds; countries like Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, and Croatia rely heavily on EU funding, using approximately 85% of their WiD budgets from the EU.

Fig. 16 Proportion of Cohesion Fund, dedicated to WiD related projects in each country

Source: Created by the authors.

Coming back to absolute number analysis, there are 9 countries, which do not have project neither in gender equality category, nor in WiD related topic. Those are Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Ireland, Latvia, Luxemburg, Malta and Netherlands. In some project descriptions from these countries, references are made to gender considerations, such as commitments to include both women and men, ensure gender balance, or even prioritize women as a higher proportion of beneficiaries. While such mentions suggest an awareness of gender inclusivity, they might often fall short of implementing tailored strategies that address structural barriers that women and girls face in accessing and participating in the digital sector. Projects that aim to balance participation numerically may contribute to visibility, but without dedicated outreach or supportive measures specifically developed for women, they risk reinforcing rather than transforming existing inequalities. In contrast, Women in Digital initiatives are characterised by a direct focus on women and girls as a primary target group and are

built around methods and goals that intentionally promote their engagement, empowerment, and long-term participation in the digital economy.

An analysis of Cohesion Fund project descriptions reveals notable differences in how EU Member States approach gender equality, particularly in the context of digital transformation. Several country-specific practices and focus areas emerged:

- Austria focuses less on general WiD initiatives and more on supporting migrant women and addressing regional disparities. Basic ICT education is emphasized to ensure digital inclusion for everyday life, not just career advancement.
- Belgium supports digital skill development, with additional emphasis on French language training among women.
- Bulgaria prioritizes upskilling initiatives targeting company employees broadly, where women are included as part of general workforce development, rather than through gender-specific digital empowerment strategies.
- Cyprus implements workforce training initiatives inclusive of women but lacks projects explicitly focused on advancing women's participation in the digital sector.
- Croatia lacks initiatives explicitly targeting girls or women in digital areas.
- Czechia promotes upskilling programs targeting both genders, with women-centered initiatives primarily concentrated in niche sectors such as healthcare and maternity support, rather than addressing digital inclusion.
- Denmark has a limited project pool (only 295) and no distinct focus on women.
- Estonia concentrates on projects, oriented to both girls/women and boys/men.
- Finland frequently addresses gender balance and equality, although many projects target both genders equally.

- France promotes diversity - focused projects, support training for migrants and both younger and older individuals, and encourage women's entrepreneurship and start-up development. However, some projects maintain a focus on traditionally feminized sectors, such as healthcare and cleaning services, which may reinforce occupational segregation.
- Germany has launched dedicated calls for women in digital projects, reflecting institutional commitment to advancing gender equality within digital transformation.
- Greece's gender-sensitive programs emphasize entrepreneurship and digitalization, integrating childcare service provision to support shared caregiving roles and labour market participation for both genders. These recurring projects focus on promoting work-life balance beyond maternity-specific support.
- Hungary prioritizes women-led business development and policies facilitating work-life reconciliation, aligning with broader gender equality objectives in economic participation.
- Ireland's project landscape shows limited focus on gender-specific digital empowerment, with few targeted initiatives for women.
- Italy usually is targeting both girls/women and boys/men, with a large volume of projects due to small-scale and often replicated initiatives across regions.
- Latvia's digital projects do not specifically address women's empowerment or gender equality in digital contexts.
- Lithuania has implemented gender analysis at the municipal level but lacks substantial projects directly targeting women in digital fields.
- Luxemburg's initiatives lack a specific focus on gender or women's empowerment within digital transformation.

- Malta's small project portfolio predominantly addresses women's mental health concerns, such as suicide prevention, not their empowering in digital area.
- The Netherlands includes women as a target group in various projects, but these efforts are not specifically oriented towards digital empowerment.
- Poland mandates gender-disaggregated beneficiary data and promotes gender equality broadly; however, it seldom prioritizes women-specific empowerment within digital contexts.
- Portugal's projects often ensure non-discrimination and include women in employment targets but lack a dedicated focus on women's specific needs in digital sectors.
- Romania exhibits considerable use of gender-disaggregated data and women's promotion, though WiD-specific projects remain sparse.
- Slovakia is oriented on people upskilling, training and dedicate the project to both girls/women and boys/men.
- Slovenia does not distinctly identify women as a targeted beneficiary group in its digital initiatives.
- Spain demonstrates continuity and replication of WiD projects, reflecting sustained commitment, though with limited diversification of approaches.
- Sweden has numerous projects addressing multiple demographic groups, including women, older adults, and emphasizing gender equality as a core principle.

The key observations from each country highlight diverse strategies and approaches toward addressing gender equality in digital transformation, clearly reflected in the project narratives. In short, examining Cohesion Fund allocations is not merely about tracking expenditures – it's about uncovering the political will to address gender

disparities in the digital space. It reveals whether countries are translating EU values into action, or whether more robust mechanisms are needed to ensure that women are not left behind in Europe's digital future. The wide variation in approaches underscores the multiplicity of pathways toward achieving gender-responsive digital inclusion across the EU.

2.3. Results of women in digital initiative popularity estimation

Results of all 3 data sources (public internet, RRF and Cohesion funds) illustrate quite different situation among EU MS. Trying to summarize the analysis results, 4 metrics are normalized and aggregated into one final score, to rank the MS:

- Number of operational initiatives, available in the MS as national ones (see Fig. 4).
- Ratio of RRF funding allocated to gender equality (see Fig. 6).
- Ratio of Cohesion Fund budget, dedicated to gender equality intervention category (see Fig. 11).
- Ratio of Cohesion Fund projects related to Women in Digital topic (see Fig. 14).

Using min-max normalization, each metric was scaled to express where each Member State stands as a percentage within the range of observed values across all countries (see Table 1).

Table 1. List of EU MS and normalized values of their performance in different aspects of WiD initiatives

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Country	Operational initiatives	RRF funding on gender equality	Cohesion gender equality	Cohesion WiD projects	Final score	Rank
Austria	0%	19%	100%	100%	54%	1
Germany	100%	4%	46%	5%	41%	2
Italy	86%	31%	14%	2%	35%	3
Sweden	14%	100%	0%	32%	34%	4
Czechia	29%	32%	85%	2%	32%	5
Ireland	71%	47%	0%	0%	31%	6
Belgium	71%	3%	0%	24%	29%	7
Spain	86%	4%	7%	3%	29%	8
Romania	71%	19%	0%	2%	26%	9
Finland	0%	21%	54%	28%	23%	10
Lithuania	71%	0%	1%	0%	22%	11
Greece	14%	1%	83%	0%	21%	12
Slovakia	0%	26%	41%	1%	14%	13
Poland	43%	2%	0%	1%	14%	14
Hungary	29%	11%	0%	3%	11%	15
France	29%	0%	0%	8%	11%	16
Portugal	14%	31%	1%	0%	11%	17
Malta	29%	0%	0%	0%	9%	18
Bulgaria	14%	5%	0%	0%	5%	19
Latvia	14%	3%	0%	0%	5%	20
Cyprus	0%	21%	0%	0%	4%	21
Estonia	0%	5%	0%	0%	1%	22
Slovenia	0%	0%	0%	2%	0%	23
Croatia	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%	24
Netherlands	0%	2%	0%	0%	0%	25
Denmark	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	26-27
Luxemburg	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	26-27

Recognizing that the first and fourth metrics directly address WiD-specific efforts, they were assigned a higher weight of 0.3 each, while the remaining two metrics, reflecting broader gender equality funding, were weighted at 0.2 each. These weighted normalized values were then summed to produce the final WiD engagement score for each country.

The ranking reveals that Austria leads in the Cohesion Fund indicators, Germany in operational initiatives, and Sweden in RRF gender equality allocations. Consequently, these three countries occupy the top positions in the overall ranking. While the score may be subject to debate considering factors such as country size, timing of initiatives, and actual impact the availability of quantifiable WiD-related data provides a valuable preliminary snapshot of the digital gender equality landscape across EU Member States.

Analysing the results reveal an interesting pattern, Austria ranks in the TOP10 for RRF and Cohesion funding rankings, however, have no publicly visible operational initiatives. This can be affected by limited search on the internet, but at the same time it could indicate the “market” is filled with national initiatives, available to certain target groups and there is no need for publicly visible, established by individuals or associations, inviting to join everyone. Similar tendency is visible in the case of Finland.

Germany, Italy, Czechia, and Spain stand out as countries that apply a systematic approach to promoting women in digital (WiD). These countries show consistent engagement across all evaluation criteria, with no zero values recorded. This demonstrates how the use of diverse and coordinated measures can effectively contribute to a common goal: increasing women's participation in the digital sector.

In contrast, Denmark and Luxembourg illustrate cases where national-level attention to the WiD topic appears limited or absent. The reasons behind the relatively inactive role of these countries in the WiD domain are not explored in this deliverable. Therefore, the scoreboard should not be interpreted as a comprehensive reflection of the actual WiD situation in these countries. Instead, it highlights the visibility and active engagement of countries in addressing the WiD agenda.

3. Methodology of initiative search and mapping

To explore and understand the landscape of Women in Digital initiatives, a mixed-methods approach was employed that integrated human insight, expert validation, and machine-assisted data gathering and analysis. This multi-layered methodology ensured a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the subject, drawing from both qualitative and quantitative sources.

The principal schema of the initiative collection and analysis is presented in figure 17. The human based actions are marked in magenta colour, while technology-fused – in violet.

Fig. 17 General schema of WiD initiative data collection and analysis

Source: Created by the authors.

A detailed description of each action is presented in the following section. The main objective was to gather diverse data sources and, in parallel, collect data on WiD initiatives focused on both operational initiative identification and initiative funding. The first aspect reflects the activity levels of Member States and their capacity to implement WiD empowerment initiatives, while the second highlights the allocation of resources aimed at addressing WiD challenges.

3.1. Identification of possible data sources

The main data sources were identified by revising existing reports and dashboards on Women in Digital area. Given the geographical focus on European countries, information systems maintained by the European Commission were also examined for relevant data.

Inspecting each potential data source, it was evaluated based on several criteria:

- **Trustworthiness** - Is the data source trusted? Only data from reputable organizations was considered. Sources such as unofficial or compromised websites were excluded to ensure reliability.
- **Accessibility** - Is the data available for analysis? The data source had to be available with no restrictions for reading and non-commercial usage.
- **Geographical scope** - Does the data include geographical data (country or continent) to map it to appropriate MS? The data needed to include geographic identifiers (country, region, or continent) to accurately map initiatives to specific Member States or broader European/global coverage.
- **Relevance to WiD** - Does the data contain WiD leaky pipeline phases and/or funding information? Data sources had to provide information related to the Women in Digital leaky pipeline phases and/or funding details. This included

structured or descriptive information on target groups or allocated funding for initiatives.

- Suitability for Automated Analysis - Is the data suitable for automated extraction and analysis? Priority was given to data that is computer-readable and structured, enabling automated extraction and annual updates to maintain data currency.

While applying the same criteria, the list of data sources for analysis could be extended in the future. At the current stage, the list is the following:

- Recovery and Resilience Facility projects have a clear assignment to gender equality. RRF Scoreboard¹¹ already have all data about the projects. This data is well-structured, easily extractable, and represents one of the most reliable sources available. Using the Qlik Sense Hub platform, this structured RRF data can be analysed to generate insightful tables and visualizations. An example dashboard (see Fig. 18) demonstrates how total funding amounts and amounts dedicated specifically to gender equality can be displayed alongside additional information such as country, social category, measure, measure type, progress status, and more. This data gathering is very straight forward, oriented on needed dimension and measurement specification, with ability to view and download the data for further analysis. For these reasons, the RRF Scoreboard was selected as a primary data source for in-depth analysis.

¹¹ https://dashboard.tech.ec.europa.eu/qs_digit_dashboard_mt/public/hub/stream/1d5f8b8b-6b97-4642-914a-4de9d040a245

Fig. 18 Example dashboard of RRF data in Qlik Sense Hub platform, selected to reflect funding for gender equality

Source: Created by the authors.

- Kohesio system¹² has all information about projects supported by EU Cohesion policy. This data source has attribute “Category of intervention”, where category “Equality between men and women in all areas, including in access to employment, career progression, reconciliation of work and private life and promotion of equal pay for equal work”. This category provides a clear indicator of projects related to gender equality. At the same time the provided data and description of the projects can be used to identify women in digital related projects but will require human or/and ML interpretation to determine whether the projects specifically target girls and women and focus on the digital sector. Due to the breadth of available data and the importance of

¹² <https://kohesio.ec.europa.eu/en>

Cohesion Funds for EU development, this data source was also included in the analysis.

- EU Funding & Tender Portal¹³ publish main information about projects & results. After filtering for relevance to the Women in Digital topic, this data can be analysed by human experts or ML models. However, since funding decisions are based on proposal quality, this dataset primarily reflects successful projects and does not capture those that applied but did not receive funding. Consequently, this source was excluded from the current analysis scope but could serve as a valuable supplementary source in the future. Global internet (via already known initiatives, search engines and social networks) could be used to find some local, European, or non-European, global initiatives. Because this information sources are not structured, therefore the information, presented in the webpage or post have to be analysed by machine and human to assess its relevance to women in digital topic. Despite the difficulty in extracting the data and finding all existing initiatives, this data source can show initiatives, which rise from different sources, not just national or EU funding. Therefore, this data source is used for search of operational initiatives and could be exploited even deeper in the future.
- Different statistics and dashboards, summarizing the situation in WiD topic. Typically, these reports are based on state data sources, as discussed earlier, or they introduce survey data. Due to uncertainties about the original data quality and the fact that these reports often present already aggregated and analysed information, such data sources are excluded from this deliverable.

¹³ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/projects-results>

However, if a report included the original, raw data source, it was considered for further analysis.

This is the initial list of data sources used to identify Women in Digital (WiD) initiatives. Since much of the available data is unstructured and not explicitly linked to gender diversity in ICT and digital fields, a certain level of automation is required for effective processing.

To ensure both efficiency and accuracy, the data is first analysed using automated tools. These tools handle repetitive tasks such as data retrieval, structuring, and preliminary analysis. However, to maintain a high level of trust and reliability, the machine-generated results are then reviewed and validated by experts. This hybrid approach balances the speed of automation with the quality assurance provided by human oversight.

3.2. Search and mapping of operational initiatives targeting Women in Digital

To compile the list of operational initiatives, members of the WIDCON project first gathered all known initiatives related to the Women in Digital topic, as well as similar initiatives that do not strictly fall into this category such as general women empowerment programs, women in other sectors, or digital training for the broader population. The collection process included both previously known initiatives and new ones identified through search engines and collaboration with other projects. For example, STREAM-IT project has an interactive map¹⁴, which “showcases a selection of exemplary projects and initiatives designed to empower girls and women in STEAM

¹⁴ <https://virtualmakerspace.streamit-project.eu/stream-it-interactive-map/>

fields”. With permission from the STREAM-IT project members, their list of initiatives was incorporated into this deliverable, after filtering out initiatives focused solely on general STEAM promotion that may include girls but do not specifically target girls or women.

The WiD initiatives were summarized using the following fields:

- Title of the initiative.
- URL of the initiative web page (from which the texts were extracted automatically).
- Orientation towards STEM phase.
- Orientation towards ICT phase.
- Orientation towards DIGITAL phase.
- Orientation towards Leadership phase.
- Focus on research or analysis related to WiD The digital sector themes covered.
- Countries where the initiative is available.
- Specific target group characteristics or topical focus of the project.
- Number of members or participants the initiative reaches.
- Start year of the initiative.
- Types of activities offered to girls and women (such as training, mentoring, etc.).

All these fields were completed based on the known and discovered operational initiatives. To ensure consistency, avoid duplication, and address any missing data, the compiled list was reviewed by an independent reviewer. In total, 141 WiD-related initiatives were identified.

Subsequently, the WiD initiatives were further filtered to focus only on those related to the four key phases of the WiD framework. Research-only initiatives were excluded from the scope of this deliverable but were reviewed separately to identify potential additional data sources. During the initial analysis, it became evident that data on initiative membership, the number of people reached, and start dates were often incomplete or inconsistent, showing varying figures across sources. Consequently, these specific fields were omitted from the detailed analysis. The remaining data fields were utilized for the operational initiative analysis, which is presented in Section 2.1 and detailed in Annex 1.

3.3. Automated gathering of initiative funding data

Initiative funding data is gathered from RRF and Cohesion funding portals. RRF data is presented in Qlik Sense Hub platform, which allows to generate new reports, charts, selecting the relevant data, its aggregation functions and presentation types. Considering the platform functionality, all RRF data analysis was conducted within this platform, with summarized data downloaded as analysis reports.

In contrast, the Cohesion Fund data lacks such a detailed analysis tool and is provided in a user-oriented format, displayed as project lists with filtering options and map visualizations, and allows downloading project lists per country. While attempting to scrape data directly from the web interface, a limitation was discovered: starting from page 66, the results of page 65 repeat on all subsequent pages, preventing complete data scraping.

Therefore, project lists for each country were downloaded instead¹⁵. The data was retrieved on May 9, 2025, selecting the “latest” available period and excluding INTERREG projects. The size of the downloaded *.xlsx files varied, reflecting the differing number of records per country. Altogether, these files contained information on 1,977,638 projects. Given this volume, manual review of all projects was unfeasible, so a multi-level filtering process was implemented to reduce the dataset to a manageable size for manual inspection.

3.4.ML model building

To automate identification of WiD related initiatives and projects, the textual content from their web pages was utilized. Human experts determine whether the text pertains to WiD by analysing its content. To replicate this process, several web page text analysis methods were employed to detect patterns that could distinguish WiD initiatives from the broader list of projects. The first approach was extracting key keywords commonly found in WiD-related operational initiatives, as presented on their websites, as well as in related initiatives (see Fig. 19).

The initial results were not very informative, as both categories shared many similar keywords such as women, community, support, project, and event. To improve differentiation, common keywords were removed from the word clouds. Unique keywords from the remaining terms were then used to generate distinct word clouds (see Fig. 20).

¹⁵ <https://kohesio.ec.europa.eu/en/data/projects>

Fig. 19 Word clouds from WiD operational initiative web page texts (a) and from web age text from similar initiatives (b)

Source: Created by the authors.

Fig. 20 Unique word clouds from WiD operational initiative web page texts (a) and from web age text from similar initiatives (b)

Source: Created by the authors.

These word clouds become more distinct; however, their practical value was limited since many of the specific words originated from non-English websites some available only in local languages, while others were in English. Taking this into account, it was decided to focus exclusively on English-language texts (as the Cohesion Fund data presents project titles and descriptions in English) and apply three automated methods for project description analysis:

- C1 - Does the text contain keywords, related to girls/women, such as: women, woman, girl, girls, female, gender.

- C2 - Does the text contain keywords, related to digital area, such as: digital, ICT, computer, technology, STEM.
- C3 - Does the text contain keywords, related to girls/women and the digital area.

The presence of keywords alone does not guarantee the correct context within the text. To ensure that women- and technology-related keywords appear close to each other, an additional method was introduced:

- C4 - Does the text contain at least one women-related keyword and one digital related keyword within the same sentence. Proportion of such sentences in the overall text was calculated for each text.

Despite the additional narrowing down, the combined keyword approach did not fully capture the specific semantics of the text. To estimate the semantic of the text, each sentence of the text was converted into vector, using multi-language SBERT model (all-MiniLM-L6-v2)¹⁶, which transforms the sentence into a 384-dimensional dense vector space. This vector was then compared to a reference vector, obtained by using text "girl girls STEM ICT woman women digital leadership female". For comparison different vector similarity methods were used. After modelling, the cosines similarity¹⁷ was selected. Those each project had two additional metrics:

- C5 - The average semantic similarity between all sentences in the project description and the reference keywords.

¹⁶ <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>

¹⁷ <https://huggingface.co/tasks/sentence-similarity>

- C6 - The maximum semantic similarity value among all sentences in the project description compared to the reference keywords.

The same 384-dimensional vector was used to predict whether the text reflects a WiD initiative or not. To achieve this, more than 20 different classification models were developed and tested. The evaluation criteria included overall accuracy and per-class accuracy, with particular emphasis on minimizing false negatives prioritizing the inclusion of potentially relevant initiatives for manual review rather than mistakenly excluding them. Finally, two were selected (see Fig. 21): SVM model achieved the highest overall classification accuracy of 75% (77% of WiD initiatives were detected correctly and 71% of non-WiD text were identified correctly) and kNN model for false-positive and overall accuracy balance, with overall classification accuracy of 67% (85% of WiD initiatives were detected correctly and 43% of non-WiD text were identified correctly).

Fig. 21 Confusion matrixes for WiD prediction for overall (a) and for false-positive (b) oriented cases

Source: Created by the authors.

Building a machine learning model with a limited dataset of only 263 initiatives poses significant challenges, making high accuracy unrealistic at this stage. Taking this into account, two additional metrics were added:

- C7 - Probability of the WiD class, using kNN model.
- C8 - Probability of the WiD class, using SVM model.

Those 8 metrics were calculated for each project as supplemented columns for record filtering. To estimate the logic which of these metrics is important, what importance it has – iterative process was done, with the help of experts manual labelling. 3000 records were revised fully manually to estimate the threshold values and logic for record filtering, ensuring no WiD initiatives will be missed. So, the records were filtered to 295312 records, which is about 15% of all records. It was done with this logic – if C1 (at least 1 women related keyword is mentioned) or C2 (at least 1 digital related keyword is mentioned) or C3>0 (women and digital keywords used) or C4>0 (women and digital keywords mentioned in one sentence) or C5>0.3 (average semantic similarity) or C6>0.4 (maximum semantic similarity) or C7>0.8 (kNN model prediction for WiD class) or C9>0.9 (SVM model prediction for WiD class).

This approach still generated a very large number of candidate projects, but only about 0.15% were ultimately confirmed as true WiD initiatives. This indicates that while the model could be improved, it was intentionally tuned to avoid false-negative cases, leaving too high false-positive rate.

Each country exhibits unique characteristics in how projects are described. As noted in the Cohesion Fund data analysis section, some countries embed gender equality requirements broadly across many projects, even when the project itself is not directly

related to Women in Digital initiatives. This pattern is reflected in the ratio of filtered projects versus confirmed WiD initiatives, as shown in Figure 22.

Fig. 22 Ratios of records after the filtering and manual revision

Source: Created by the authors.

For example, 57% of Swedish projects required manual review, with similarly high percentages (over 30%) observed in Finland, Greece, Hungary, Denmark, Czechia, Poland, and Romania. Conversely, Austria had the highest proportion of confirmed WiD projects at 4.2%, followed by Belgium, Finland, Sweden, and Italy, which ranged from 0.75% to 0.35%.

At the current stage, the automation process was not tightly integrated with manual review, as the priority was to strike a balance that ensures no WiD initiatives are overlooked. Initial experiments involving 3,000 records from various countries, combined with iterative adjustments to filtering thresholds, have increased confidence in the results. However, some uncertainty remains—certain initiatives might be missed

due to highly varied language use or insufficient project descriptions. Additionally, the method currently only processes English-language texts.

4. Discussion

The analysis of Women in Digital initiatives across Europe reveals both encouraging momentum and significant gaps in the journey toward digital gender equality. The report highlights the persistent underrepresentation of women across all stages of the digital pipeline – STEM education, ICT specialization, digital workforce participation, and leadership. It maps operational initiatives, funding patterns, and national-level commitments, offering a structured view of how European Member States are responding to the WiD Declaration.

4.1. Conclusions

Analysing the received results, the following conclusions could be derived:

- A high concentration of initiatives is found in ICT and Digital career phases, with fewer in STEM and particularly in Leadership. The shortage of leadership-focused initiatives is a critical gap, as leadership roles are essential for driving systemic change and serving as role models in the digital sector. This underrepresentation reflects a significant structural barrier, since leadership positions are key to challenging entrenched gender norms and shaping inclusive organizational cultures. Without targeted interventions at the leadership level, efforts to achieve gender equality risk remaining superficial, as meaningful systemic transformation requires women's visibility and influence in decision-making positions.
- Countries such as Austria, Germany, and Sweden lead in different aspects – Austria in Cohesion Fund usage, Germany in operational initiatives, and Sweden in RRF funding for gender equality. However, a significant number of countries, including Denmark, Luxembourg, and Malta, have little to no visible

activity in this area, raising questions about regional situation and/or imbalances in gender inclusion. This uneven distribution points to persistent regional disparities in gender mainstreaming. It suggests that some Member States may lack political will, resources, or expertise to implement Women in Digital initiatives, exacerbating digital gender divides within the EU. Although the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and Cohesion Funds offer mechanisms to support gender equality, only about 3.4% of RRF funding is dedicated to such efforts, and an even smaller fraction of Cohesion Fund-supported projects are directly related to the WiD topic. This marginal financial commitment is indicative of gender equality being side-lined in budgetary priorities. It reflects a lack of gender-responsive budgeting, where funding is not systematically allocated to address gendered barriers in digital sectors. Unlike some global counterparts, especially in the USA which target sub-groups like Black or Muslim women, most European initiatives focus solely on gender, without addressing intersecting inequalities related to ethnicity, migration status, or socio-economic background.

- A narrow focus on gender alone overlooks the intersectionality of discrimination. Ignoring how ethnicity, socio-economic status, migration status or other axes differentiation compound digital exclusion risks leaving behind the most marginalized women. Intersectional approaches are vital to ensure inclusivity within Women in Digital initiatives.
- There's often a disconnect between publicly visible (operational) initiatives and those supported by national or EU funding. This may point to internal national efforts not widely publicized or a lack of strategic visibility planning, undermining awareness and accessibility.

- Initiatives like ECWT demonstrate the value of integrated, multi-phase approaches, but such examples remain rare. The current landscape is fragmented, and best practices are not systematically shared or scaled. Fragmentation undermines scalability and sustainability of gender equality gains. Integrated approaches that address multiple phases of the pipeline from education to leadership are essential for comprehensive impact. The EU should prioritize platforms for knowledge exchange and institutionalize best practices to accelerate progress.

4.2.Future work

The deliverable presents findings exclusively on the existence and visibility of gender equality and Women in Digital initiatives; it does not provide a comprehensive assessment of the overall WiD situation in each Member State. To achieve a deeper and more nuanced analysis of WiD status, additional primary and secondary data collection is necessary. This task is planned within the WIDCON project framework, which aims to develop a comprehensive WiD index based on richer datasets.

It is important to acknowledge that some initiatives may have been overlooked due to limited online visibility, language-specific search challenges, or variations in keyword usage to describe the initiatives. Therefore, Member States, organizations, and individuals with knowledge of existing WiD initiatives in specific EU countries are encouraged to contribute by providing feedback and sharing additional initiatives. This collaboration will enable ongoing updates and refinement of the report, leading to a more accurate and representative overview of the current WiD landscape.

To support the further collection of operational initiatives, a web crawler will be created. It will gather the web page content and in automated way will estimate the potential of

the website to represent WiD initiative. To implement it, the WiD classificatory will be improved, adding the Cohesion Fund data, both in English as well as local language, to increase the model accuracy. While the final validation and categorization will remain an expert-driven process, this automation will significantly accelerate data gathering and reduce manual workload, enabling a more comprehensive and up-to-date understanding of WiD initiatives across Europe.

5. Annex I. Initial list of operational initiatives targeting Women in Digital topic

Table 2. List of initiatives on Women in Digital

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Initiative	STEM	ICT	DIGITAL	LEADERSHIP	Geography	Field	Specifics
50intech			yes		France	ICT	
Accenture Girls in Tech	yes	yes	yes		Global	ICT	
Ada Lovelace Projekt	yes	yes	yes		Germany	STEM	
Ai4All Foundation	yes	yes	yes	yes	Europe	AI	
AllWomen		yes	yes		Spain	AI, ICT	
AnitaB		yes	yes		Global	Technologies	
Asociación Women Angels For STEAM				yes	Spain	Digital	
Be Digital Together	yes	yes	yes		Belgium	STEM, ICT	
BeWiSe		yes	yes		Belgium	STEM	
Black Women in Tech			yes		Global	STEM	
BlockW	yes	yes	yes	yes	Ireland	Technology and digital	
CyberMentor	yes				Germany	STEM	
Code First: Girls		yes	yes		Global	Technology	
Codette	yes	yes			Romania	Technology, ICT	
Connecting Women in Technology Ireland	yes	yes	yes		Ireland	Technology	
Czechitas		yes	yes		Czechia	Cybersecurity and AI	

Initiative	STEM	ICT	DIGITAL	LEADERSHIP	Geography	Field	Specifics
Dare IT			yes		Poland	ICT	
DevelopHer		yes	yes	yes	UK	ICT	
DigiGirLz	yes				Global	STEAM	
Digital female entrepreneurs				yes	Spain	Digitalization and AI	
Digital Girls Summer Camp (Ragazze Digiali Summer Camp)	yes				Italy	Digital	
Digital Marketing Women Employability and Entrepreneurship Program		yes	yes		Global	Digital marketing	
Digital Media Women			yes		Germany	Digital media	
Digital Women			yes		UK	ICT	
DigitHer Initiative		yes	yes		Italy	Data engineering, JAVA developer	
Diversity in Tech (Women in Digital Tech)			yes	yes	Ireland	Technology	
Django Girls		yes	yes		Global	ICT	Django community
Donne in Digitale				yes	Italy	Digital	
ECWT	yes	yes	yes	yes	Europe	ICT	
EQUALS-EU	yes	yes	yes		Europe	Informatics	
EUGAIN		yes			Europe	Math	
European Girls' Mathematical Olympiad (EGMO)	yes	yes			Europe	Math, data analysis	
European Girls' Olympiad in Informatics (EGOI)	yes	yes			Europe	ICT	
EWPN (European Women Payments Network)			yes	yes	Europe	STEM	
Female Empowerment in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics in Higher Education (FeSTEM)		yes			Europe	STEM	
Female Tech leaders				yes	Global	Technology	
Female Techpreneur			yes	yes	Global	STEM	
Femmes Numérique			yes		France	Digital	

Initiative	STEM	ICT	DIGITAL	LEADERSHIP	Geography	Field	Specifics
Femtec	yes	yes	yes		Germany	STEAM, ICT	
FemTech Collective			yes		Global	Innovations	
Furt'Her			yes	yes	Global	Blockchain and AI	
FUTURE WOMEN		yes	yes		Europe	Digital	
GENDER STI - Gender Equality in Science, Technology and Innovation Bilateral and Multilateral Dialogues			yes		Europe	Science, technology	
GE-STEAM: GENDER EQUALITY IN SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING, ART AND MATHEMATICS	yes				Europe	STEM	
Girl who code	yes	yes			Global	ICT	
Girls code fun	yes				Poland	ICT	
Girls Go Circular	yes	yes	yes	yes	Europe	Technology	
Girls in ICT	yes	yes			Global	ICT	
Girls in STEAM academy	yes				Greece	Technology	
Girls in Tech	yes	yes			Global	ICT	
Girls4STEM	yes				Spain	STEM	
Global Tech Advocates Black Women in Tech			yes		UK	ICT	
international Women in Tech			yes		Global	Technology	
You equal tech			yes		Global	Digital	
idisen game jam		yes			Belgium	Games	
ISG Women in Digital				yes	Global	Technology	
IT's for girls!	yes				Czech Republic	ICT	
Konferencija „Ar STEAM mokslai tik vyrams“ (VDU)			yes		Lithuania	Technology	
LATAM Women in Cybersecurity	yes	yes	yes		Global	Cybersecurity	

Initiative	STEM	ICT	DIGITAL	LEADERSHIP	Geography	Field	Specifics
Malta Digital Innovation Authority	yes		yes		Malta	Digital	
Milion Women Mentors	yes	yes	yes		Global	ICT	
Mint Zukunft schaffen	yes				Germany	STEAM	
More Girls in STEAM (MOGIS)	yes	yes	yes		Serbia	STEM	
National Network of Community Juries for Artificial Intelligence			yes	yes	Italy	AI	
PyGirls	yes				Global	ICT	
Portuguese Women in Tech			yes		Portugal	ICT	
Rails Girls		yes	yes		Global	Programming	
Rails Girls Berlin		yes	yes		Germany	Programming	
Riga TechGirls	yes	yes	yes	yes	Latvia	Technology	
Robotikos akademija / Tapk kūrėja	yes				Lithuania	ICT, robotics	
Robotikos mokykla / Tech princesė	yes				Lithuania	STEM	
S.HE Goes Digital: Training in digital and IT essentials		yes	yes		Belgium	STEM	
She can code			yes		Global	STEM	
SHE CHOOSES STEM FOR THE FUTURE		yes			Europe	STEM	
She Codes		yes	yes		Israel	Programming	
She figures				yes	Europe	Tech	
She Tech Italy		yes	yes		Italy	ICT	
SheTransformsIT		yes	yes		Germany	ICT	
STAR Girls - Supporting Talent & Ambition in Renewable Energy Sector for Girls, through mentoring and role models	yes				Europe	Engineering	
STEAM Summer School for Girls	yes				Lithuania	STEM	
STEAMbrace	yes				Europe	STEM	
STEM Talent Girls	yes	yes			Spain	STEM	

Initiative	STEM	ICT	DIGITAL	LEADERSHIP	Geography	Field	Specifics
Stem Women			yes		Global	STEM	
STEM Women Congress	yes	yes	yes	yes	Global	STEM	
STEM4GIRLS UC3M	yes				Spain	STEM	
STEMettes	yes	yes	yes		UK	STEAM	
STEMpont	yes	yes			Hungary	STEM	
STEMsisters		yes	yes		Hungary	STEM	
StreamIT	yes	yes			Europe	STEAM	
Strong Women in IT			yes		Poland	ICT	
Tech She Can	yes				Global	Technology	
TechFemme			yes		Cameroon	ICT	
Tech.mt	yes				Malta	Technology	
Technovation Girls / Girls for a Change	yes				Global	ICT	
Technovation Girls Romania	yes				Romania	Digital	
TechSisters		yes	yes		Global	ICT	Muslim
Techsoup Lietuva		yes	yes		Global	ICT	
TechUp Women / Click start		yes	yes		UK	Technology	
TechWomen			yes		Global	STEM	
THE ASSOCIATION OF WOMEN IN ENGINEERING, SCIENCE, AND TECHNOLOGY (AFIST)		yes	yes		Romania	STEM	
The Girl Project Ada		yes			Norway	ICT	
THE INTERNATIONAL GIRL'S DAY IN ICT IN SERBIA		yes		yes	Serbia	ICT	
The National Center for Women & Information Technology (NCWIT)		yes	yes		Global	STEM	
The Women's Digital Academy			yes		UK	ICT	
TryEngineering IEEE/Girls in STEM Events	yes				Global	STEM	

Initiative	STEM	ICT	DIGITAL	LEADERSHIP	Geography	Field	Specifics
UNIDIR Women in AI Fellowship			yes		Global	AI	
We Shape Tech			yes		Switzerland	ICT	
WiTechNetwork		yes	yes		Sweden	ICT	
Women and AI			yes		Global	AI	
Women and Girls in STEM Forum		yes	yes		Europe	STEM	
Women Choose Tech		yes	yes		Ireland	Technology	
Women for Security			yes		Italy	Cybersecurity	
Women in AI		yes	yes		Global	AI	
Women in Big Data			yes		Global	Big data / data analytics	
Women in Cyber / Women in Cybersecurity / WiCys		yes	yes		Global	Cybersecurity	
Women in Cloud			yes		Global	Cloud computing, digital transformation	
Women in coding Community		yes	yes		Global	Coding	
Women in Data Science (WiDS)			yes		Global	Data science, machine learning, analytics	
Women in Data Science (WiDS) Worldwide			yes		Romania	ICT	
Women in Digital (WID)		yes	yes		Global	ICT	
Women in Engineering Society (WES)		yes	yes		UK	Engineering	
Women in Fintech			yes		Global	Fintech	
Women in Machine Learning (WiML)			yes	yes	Global	AI, ethics, innovations	
Women in Mobility			yes		Europe	Transport	
Women in security and privacy			yes		Global	STEM	

Initiative	STEM	ICT	DIGITAL	LEADERSHIP	Geography	Field	Specifics
Women in STEM – Overcoming Stereotypes	yes	yes	yes		Bulgaria	STEM	
Women in STEM (WISE)		yes	yes		USA	ICT	
Women in Stem Fellowship		yes	yes		Belgium	STEM	
Women in STEM Scholarship			yes		Europe	STEM	
Women in Tech		yes	yes		Global	STEM	
Women in Tech Cluj			yes		Romania	ICT	
Women in Tech EU			yes	yes	Europe	Technology	
Women in Tech Network			yes	yes	Global	ICT	
Women in Technology & Science Ireland		yes	yes		Ireland	Engineering, technologies, math, science	
Women Plus			yes		Switzerland	ICT	
Women STEM UP		yes	yes		Europe	STEM	
Women Techmakers			yes		Global	Technology	
Women Who Code		yes	yes		Global	Data science, programming, AI	
Women Who Tech			yes		Europe	Technology	
WOMEN2INVEST PROGRAMME				yes	Global	STEM	
Women4Cyber		yes	yes		Global	Cybersecurity	
Women4tech	yes	yes	yes		Europe	ICT	
WomenGoTech		yes	yes		Lithuania	ICT	
Ada Developer Academy			yes		USA	ICT	Black, Latine, Indigenous Americans, Native Hawaiian & Pacific Islander, LGBTQIA+,

Initiative	STEM	ICT	DIGITAL	LEADERSHIP	Geography	Field	Specifics
							and low-income people
Black girls code	yes	yes			USA, South Africa	Technologies, STEM	Black girls
Digital Undivided			yes	yes	USA	Digital	Black and Latinx women
Girl Geek X		yes	yes		USA	ICT	
Girls Go Tech	yes				Hong Kong	ICT	
She Code Africa	yes	yes	yes		Pan-African	Digital	
She++			yes	yes	USA	ICT	
STEM connector			yes		USA	Technology	
Tech Girls	yes				USA	ICT	
Tech Sisters		yes	yes		Middle East, North Africa	Technology, innovation	
The National Girls Collaborative Project (NGCP)	yes	yes			USA	ICT	

6. Annex II. List of WiD related projects among Cohesion Funds

Table 2. List of projects on Women in Digital

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Initiative title	Country
Basic education for refugee women	Austria
Basic education for migrant women	Austria
A lot of knowledge ePSA	Austria
MAFALDA BOX	Austria
Learning box	Austria
Computer courses and orientation towards the labour market	Austria
Green Technology Innovation	Austria
Founders 4.0	Austria
Base for everyone!	Austria
Basic education with digital applications for women	Austria
learn forever	Austria
Resisters: Basic education for migrant women	Austria
Open up: Basic education courses for migrants/refugees	Austria
Basic education with digital applications for women	Austria
learn forever	Austria
DigiKomm Digitalisation. Advice. Communication Offers to secure livelihoods and increase employment for women with migration or refugee experience	Austria
Basic education for women with ICT	Austria
learn forever	Austria
Basic education courses for women (migrants): Literacy; German/ICT; Basic education courses for young migrant women: German/English, Mathematics/ICT	Austria
SBB Women 2.0 – Interface Education & Work Interface Assistance in STEM	Austria
ABZ*digi4work – Promoting women’s digital skills for work 4.0	Austria
Fair – Women: Arriving, informing, realising	Austria
Basic education with digital applications for women	Austria
Learning box	Austria
Girls – Ready for Technology	Austria
Skilled Workers-Intensive Training (FIA) Machining Technology	Austria
Alom basic formation	Austria
Learning box	Austria
ACIS CLAIRVAL “I-Mediat” I.S.P.	Belgium
Gender-and-ICT	Belgium
Artlab	Belgium

Initiative title	Country
ICT Qualifying Training — ISP Women	Belgium
Women and ICT Qualifying Training — Explore3	Belgium
Girl Power/Girls and Technology	Belgium
Focus on Technical Talent	Belgium
I'LL DO BETTER! — opportunity for women in the Zlín Region to apply in fields with higher wages	Czechia
Alone, but strong: We eliminate discrimination against single mothers in the labour market	Czechia
Development of women in STEM fields – health care	Czechia
Logistics for the future	Czechia
Moms, even IT helps	Czechia
Labour market for all	Czechia
The little girl knows the world.	Czechia
Innovative workout design for women	Czechia
New templates for Girl's Catholic High School	Czechia
STEM fields for women	Czechia
Support of the School of All-Women	Czechia
Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, “Multimedia Pop-Up Learning Lab Make Up Your MINT”	Germany
“Feminin across the country”, cooperation project Hochschule Merseburg and Otto-von-Guericke University Magdeburg	Germany
React-EU Resilience Strengthening and Digitalisation	Germany
Gender-sensitive Office-Online-Digitalisation in Knowledge and Document Management in North Hesse SMEs (GOOD)	Germany
Innovative STEM funding for young talent Cologne 4.0	Germany
The “invisible staff” — Equal treatment of staff in technology and administration (MTV) at universities	Germany
Empowering migrant women	Germany
Promotion of Science and Research (WiFo), preparation for career entry	Germany
With STEM – Regional Strategy Concept for Women in STEM	Germany
Impetus for labour market policy (Idea)	Germany
Climb Up — Career steps for women in leadership in the digital world of work	Germany
React-EU Resilience Strengthening and Digitalisation	Germany
#4.0 — Blended Working. Digital competence and work-life balance for Berlin SMEs	Germany
FIB “Women in employment”	Germany
Madame digital	Germany
Service point guide – Support for female start-ups	Germany
Regional Innovation Promotions Uni Leipzig 2016	Germany
Regional Innovation Promotions Uni Leipzig 2017	Germany
Al Amal's Hope	Germany
Alp HS KO Koblenz and Höhr-Grenzhausen 2018	Germany
New Work Women — Women in the Digital Transformation	Germany

Initiative title	Country
sparkX — The Leadership Program for Women in Media Enterprises	Germany
Female Leadership in Digital Excellence	Germany
Lea-digital Digital Learning & Work Forms for Migrants	Germany
Back2Job	Germany
We're here!	Germany
FIA	Germany
Me. It's easy. Digital. The digital program for women to re-enter the professional world	Germany
Impetus for labour market policy (IdeA)	Germany
Impetus for labour market policy (IdeA)	Germany
Balance in the digital transformation — opportunity digital	Germany
PAMIRA	Germany
Esperanza 4.0	Germany
MeCoSa, OVGU Magdeburg	Germany
I can digitally!	Germany
Digital care	Germany
Raising awareness and empowerment of actors on gender equality and non-discrimination against women: Project “Let’s MINT”	Germany
Selfie – So Successful Learning Women’s Initiative Developing	Germany
React-EU Resilience Strengthening and Digitalisation	Germany
BIPoC women	Germany
State Innovation Promotions University of Leipzig 2017-2	Germany
State Innovation Promotions University of Leipzig 2018	Germany
State Innovation Promotions University of Leipzig 2019	Germany
Start-up consultations by granting start-up passports – Frauenurinal in mobile and fixed sanitary facilities especially for women with digital app —	Germany
“Crafts with FiF – smart, networked and digital”	Germany
IndiWAA	Germany
Raising awareness and empowerment of actors on gender equality and non-discrimination against women: Support and promotion of women in STEM professions	Germany
Preparation of an inventory “Women in Tech”	Germany
ADA Lovelace project: Mint-Regio-Zentrum JGU Mainz	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project TU Kaiserslautern	Germany
ADA Lovelace project: Mint-Regio-Zentrum JGU Mainz	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project at Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project at Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Central Coordination Office 2016	Germany
ADA Lovelace project: Competence Center for Women in STEM, University Koblenz-LD, Sp Studies & Training	Germany
ADA Lovelace project: Competence Center for Women in STEM, University of Koblenz-Landau, Sp Studies & Training 2019	Germany

Initiative title	Country
ADA Lovelace project: Competence Center for Women in STEM, University Ko-La, Sp Studies and Training	Germany
ADA Lovelace project: Regiozentrum Koblenz – University of Koblenz-Landau 2018	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project, Focus on Studies (HS Trier, 2015)	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project, Focus on Studies (HS Trier, 2017)	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project, Focus on Studies (HS Trier, 2018)	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project, Focus on Studies (HS Trier, 2016)	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project, Focus on Studies (HS Trier, 2019)	Germany
ADA Lovelace project	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Uni Koblenz, SP Studies and Training 2016	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project MINT-Regiozentrum Kaiserslautern	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project University of Trier 2018	Germany
ADA Lovelace project Kaiserslautern	Germany
ADA Lovelace project Kaiserslautern	Germany
ADA Lovelace project Kaiserslautern	Germany
Alp Hochschule Koblenz Remagen 2019	Germany
Alp Hochschule Koblenz Remagen 2018	Germany
Alp Hochschule Koblenz Remagen 2021	Germany
Alp Hochschule Koblenz Remagen 2020	Germany
Alp Hochschule Ko Remagen 2016	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Central Coordination Centre 2015	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project, Study and Training	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project at Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project TU Kaiserslautern	Germany
Alp Hochschule KO Remagen 2015	Germany
Alp Diversity 2015	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Kaiserslautern University of Technology	Germany
Alp HS KO Koblenz and Höhr-Grenzhausen 2015	Germany
Alp Hochschule KO Remagen 2017	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project University of Trier	Germany
Alp HS KO Koblenz and Höhr-Grenzhausen 2016	Germany
Alp HS KO Koblenz and Höhr-Grenzhausen 2017	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Central Coordination Office 2018	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Central Coordination Unit 2017	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Trier 2020	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Trier 2021	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project University of Trier 2021	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project University of Trier 2020	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project University of Trier 2019	Germany
ADA Lovelace project: Rhineland-Pfälzisches Competence Center for Women in STEM	Germany

Initiative title	Country
ADA Lovelace project: Rhineland-Pfälzisches Competence Center for Women in STEM	Germany
AWO fairy	Germany
Alp HS KO Koblenz and Höhr-Grenzhausen 2020	Germany
Alp HS KO Koblenz and Höhr-Grenzhausen 2021	Germany
Alp HS KO Koblenz and Höhr-Grenzhausen 2019	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Central Coordination Centre 2021	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Central Coordination Office 2020	Germany
ADA Lovelace Project Central Coordination Office 2019	Germany
BALANCING	Germany
Individual coaching for women in Neustadt (ICF-NW)	Germany
Women Active in the Future – ICF-NW	Germany
Promotion of young talent 4.0 – Qualifying for the future	Germany
EDKA – Acquisition of digital skills and labour market integration	Germany
“New paths – new horizons” county of Cuxhaven	Germany
Implementation of a digital learning environment for vocational education and training REACT	Germany
Mamamia	Germany
Plan F – Neumünster	Germany
PROF³I 2021 – Per Women as Entrepreneurs Subject and Leaders Initiative RLP	Germany
PROF3I 2019	Germany
Pro Excellenceia 2.0	Germany
Women active in the future KL	Germany
Women active in the future	Germany
Smart – Digital Fitness for Women	Germany
MIF	Germany
Participation in continuing education: “Training as a Women’s Circle Leader” – Claudia Neubert	Germany
Participation in continuing education “Training as a leader of women’s circles” – educational institution: Claudia Neubert	Germany
Participation in continuing education: “GFG-Mütterpflegerin®” – Society for Preparation for Birth – Family Education and Women’s Health – Bundesverband e.V. and participation in continuing education: “First Aid for the Child” – DRK Kreisverband Leipzig-Land e.V.	Germany
Participation in continuing education: “Training as a Women’s Circle Leader” – Meeting Yourself Claudia Neubert	Germany
ERDF-zdi TP1 MINT thrilled! Win more SMEs and educational institutions for the work of the zdi Centre per STEM GT	Germany
Digital Leadership — Gender Sensible Leadership in the Digital Age	Germany
Women actively in the future	Germany
Fi 30a – Digital learning accompaniment in IBA – Tortoise GmbH	Germany
Fira – Women in the regional labour market	Germany

Initiative title	Country
Training and Support to Entrepreneurship and Integration Workplace of Collectives at Risk of Social Exclusion for Economic and Social Regeneration of Area Urban Functional Beds.	Spain
Actions aimed at the different groups of the Barrio de la Caridad, in order to eliminate the digital divide in the population (LA 4)	Spain
Effectiveness of the use of information and communication technologies in increasing physical activity and weight loss in obese and sedentary subjects. ECA. Study EVIDENT III.	Spain
Ceres and REA. 2013-2016	Spain
Ceres and REA 2016-2019	Spain
Ceres and REA 2013-2016	Spain
Ceres and REA 2016-2019	Spain
Ceres and REA 2016-2019	Spain
Ceres and REA. 2013-2016	Spain
Ceres and REA. 2013-2016	Spain
Ceres and REA 2016-2019	Spain
Development of the DIANA Program, Initiation to the Programming of Girls and Adolescents	Spain
Development of the DIANA Program, Initiation to the Programming of Girls and Adolescents	Spain
Development of the DIANA Program, Initiation to the Programming of Girls and Adolescents	Spain
Development of the DIANA Program, Initiation to the Programming of Girls and Adolescents	Spain
Bridges for employment. Itineraries for equality	Spain
Bridges for employment. Itineraries for equality	Spain
Bridges for employment. Itineraries for equality	Spain
Bridges for employment. Itineraries for equality	Spain
Women and Technology Seminars, Training Conferences for Women's and Population Associations	Spain
Women and Technology Seminars, Training Conferences for Women's and Population Associations	Spain
Women and Technology Seminars, Training Conferences for Women's and Population Associations	Spain
Women and Technology Seminars, Training Conferences for Women's and Population Associations	Spain
Actions to promote the inclusion of women in the field of science and technology	Spain
Actions to promote the inclusion of women in the field of science and technology	Spain
Actions to promote the inclusion of women in the field of science and technology	Spain
Actions to promote the inclusion of women in the field of science and technology	Spain
DIGITAL LITERACY TRAINING ACTION 1 AND 2 EDITION	Spain
DIGITAL LITERACY — FADE FOUNDATION	Spain
Women To Work: the potential of migrant women to use the world of work	Finland

Initiative title	Country
Smart LADIES IN DIGITAL WORLD — Supporting Women’s Entrepreneurship and Leadership in the Digital World	Finland
Oona 2.0 — Entrepreneur women’s business growth through digitalisation and partner networks	Finland
NaisTech	Finland
Creative Campus 2020 — Investment Project	Finland
Potential — Stereotype Destruction Development Project	Finland
VeTek — Tensions to Technological Sectors	Finland
DiversCity — versatile and digital service design	Finland
NOW, NOW! Women, Entrepreneurship and Technology	Finland
PeliKlaani — Inclusion with creative and gamified methods	Finland
#mimmitkoodaa North Karelia	Finland
You can do it! Girls and technology	Finland
High school pupils raise the software industry	Finland
WINIT — Women in IT	Finland
Acquaintance with equality	Finland
Folding together	Finland
NASTY	Finland
Women trying together	Finland
Site	Finland
Digieiko — digital, women and leadership	Finland
Codes for Women Entrepreneurship — Utilising Smart Solutions to Support Women’s Entrepreneurship	Finland
Code — Trial culture towards equality in the digital age	Finland
Live — Increase Attraction	Finland
Women on an equal footing for careers — NAU!	Finland
Supporting the employment of fragile young people through the rise in digital skills in the field of web and mobile web development	France
2021-Furthering integration pathways to employment	France
Promoting diversity in digital professions	France
development of the skills of metallurgy workers through continuing training	France
INCLUSION OF FEMALE AUDIENCES AWAY FROM EMPLOYMENT AND PUBLIC EMPLOYMENT SERVICES	France
transfer of know-how and craftsmanship in the NRPM territory	France
PREPARATION AND ACCESS TO EMPLOYMENT 2020-2021	France
SETTING UP A WORKING SITUATION	France
Job Coaching Flo8	France
Insertion with the Feminin: User manual 2019-2020	France
Supporting the sustainability of innovative companies by women and mixed teams	France
Professional Title — Accounting Secretary LOT 23GP14 R1- FORE ALTERNANCE — RENEWING 1	France
DIGITAL HEELS	France

Initiative title	Country
Women Want Web	France
Preparation and Access to Employment 2015	France
Computer Workshop	France
TRAINING OF ARTISANS AND COLLABORATING SPOUSES	France
Supporting women towards return to employment through computer literacy	France
MOBILISATION AND EMPLOYMENT	France
JOB COACHING FLO8 2020	France
E-inclusion PLIE 2021	France
Supporting women away from employment in social and professional reintegration	France
CONTINUOUS TRAINING OF ARTISANS AND COLLABORATING SPOUSES – CMA17	France
Professionalisation of business creation networks	France
Digital Sesame 2019-2020	France
Mobilising women towards employment	France
supporting women towards the return to work through computer literacy	France
AGILITE: The concept of agility for jobseekers, specific audiences, businesses and creators.	France
Job Sponsorship 2019-2020	France
DIGITAL HEELS 2.0	France
INCLUSION OF FEMALE AUDIENCES AWAY FROM EMPLOYMENT AND PUBLIC EMPLOYMENT SERVICES	France
supporting women towards the return to work through computer literacy	France
Lot 23 GP14 — Professional title of accounting secretarial — renewal 2	France
Digital Estim for Women	France
Supporting women towards the return to work through computer literacy	France
we are growing (Development of STEM in Civil Society Organisations)	Croatia
Lungoj o drom Angla mande.. Long journey ahead of me...	Hungary
Treasure-PROGRAM, the Family Value Keeper	Hungary
Implementing educational innovations at Edutus College	Hungary
Creating opportunities for women in Nógrád	Hungary
““Bari SHEJ (Great Girl) Increasing the chances of continuing education for Roma girls”	Hungary
North Iron Woman	Hungary
Promoting the social acceptance of women in Répcementi tourism	Hungary
ESTABLISHMENT OF A WOMEN’S INFORMATION AND SERVICE CENTRE IN MAKO TO IMPROVE THE RECONCILIATION OF FAMILY WORK	Hungary
Szombathely Female	Hungary
I'M PUTTING AT STAKE A GENDER ENHANCEMENT IN STEM	Italy
THE ALL GIRLS STEM LAB	Italy
L2 — A.R.A.C.N.E. — ACTIONS TO INCREASE SKILLS, NETWORKING, EMPOWERMENT	Italy
L1 — STEM FOR WOMEN	Italy

Initiative title	Country
C.5 — GUIDANCE: CONTRASTING GENDER GAPS IN SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY ENGINEERING ARTS MATHEMATICS (STEAM) AND DIGITAL SUBJECTS	Italy
C14. ORIENTATION: CONTRASTING GENDER GAPS IN SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY ENGINEERING ARTS MATHEMATICS (STEAM) AND DIGITAL SUBJECTS	Italy
L3 — SMART PEOPLE FOR SMART COMPANIES	Italy
WOMEN FOR WOMEN — NETWORK FOR INNOVATIVE SHARING OF FAMILY CARE SERVICES	Italy
COR MEMBERSHIP OF COR WOMEN — IN.SIS. COMPUTER SYSTEMS	Italy
COR WOMEN CANDIDACY — IN.SI. COMPUTER SYSTEMS	Italy
D & D: WOMEN AND DIGITAL IN MODENA	Italy
D & D: WOMEN AND DIGITAL IN REGGIO EMILIA	Italy
“CORE COMPETENCIES” DEVELOPMENT OF ICT COMPUTING SKILLS AND IMPROVEMENT OF CUSTOMER SERVICE	Italy
OLIMPIA WOMEN’S PLATFORM	Italy
L4 Â’F5: REFRESH YOUR SKILLS!	Italy
L-1 W@RK.HER : PATHWAYS FOR EMPLOYMENT, EMPLOYABILITY AND EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN	Italy
INTERVENTION ON “EDUCATION AS A TOOL FOR OVERCOMING THE GENDER GAP” WITHIN DIDACTA DIGITAL	Italy
L1 — WE FREE TALENTS	Italy
L1 — DDD Â¿DIGITAL DIMENSION WOMAN	Italy
L4- PINK-CRATIVE-LABORATORY 4.0	Italy
L1 Â¿O.P.E.R.A. — ORGANISATION AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT FOR THE EMPOWERMENT AND RESILIENCE OF ARTISTS	Italy
DETAILS OF SERENA BIRTH	Italy
PROFESSION STEM	Italy
NEW DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE SUPPLY AND PROMOTION OF BUSINESSES IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY	Italy
WOMEN IN FORM(ACTION)	Italy
WOMEN POWER CHECK IN DIGITAL SELLING	Italy
WOMEN IN DIGITAL SELLING — USING NEW MEDIA IN SALES	Italy
L2 — WOMEN: RECONCILING WORK AND FAMILY IN SITUATIONS OF ECONOMIC CRISIS AND HEALTH EMERGENCY	Italy
L4-PROJECT WIND: WOMAN IN DIGITAL	Italy
L2 -S.W.O.T.: SMARTWORKING, WOMEN, OPPORTUNITIES, TRAINING	Italy
THE GOOD WINEMAKER 5.0	Italy
L4-DONNE PLAYERS IN CHANGE	Italy
L1 Â¿D.E.A.: DEVELOPMENT, EMPOWERMENT, ABILITY	Italy
MANAGEMENT OF DOCUMENTARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES OF THE LIBRARY-TRIESTE WOMEN’S SECTION	Italy
INTRODUCTION TO IT	Italy
C0D1NGSCHOOL	Italy
L4 DIGITAL PATHWAYS FOR WOMEN IN THE THIRD MILLENNIUM	Italy

Initiative title	Country
L4 Â: DISTINGUISHING MARKS: WOMEN, KEY ACTORS IN THEIR PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL GROWTH	Italy
IMPACT WOMAN: BUILDING A SUCCESSFUL PROFESSIONAL PATHWAY	Italy
PINK FACTOR — FEMALE EMPOWERMENT FOR BUSINESS GROWTH	Italy
E-QUALITY Â: DIGITISATION PATHWAYS FOR QUALITY WOMEN’S EMPLOYMENT	Italy
L1- WWW Â: WORLD WORKING WOMEN	Italy
EVENT MANAGER	Italy
SOCIAL AND DIGITAL WOMEN	Italy
WOMEN’S SK.IN.: WOMEN’S SKILLS FOR INNOVATION	Italy
L4 — FAOWOAN	Italy
L1 — FABWOMAN FOR ECONOMIC RECOVERY	Italy
KANTIERI FOR THE LITTLE ONES	Italy
L1: VROOOM! ACCELERATING THE INNOVATION OF WOMEN’S SKILLS IN FASHION AND DESIGN BETWEEN DIGITAL MANUFACTURING AND VIRTUAL REALITY	Italy
PINK DIGITAL REVOLUTION	Italy
BLIFE: 3 YEARS LATER, THE WOMEN’S LEAP TOWARDS GREATER COMPANY AUTOMATION	Italy
PER.L.E. Â: PATHS OF LEADERSHIP AND EMPOWERMENT	Italy
SCUOLINNOVATIVA	Italy
SCUOLINNOVATIVA 2	Italy
FROM CODYROBY TO ROBOTICS I CREATE EXPLORATION AND PLAY TO LEARN	Italy
L2 Â: COOPERATION PINK: FEMALE EMPOWERMENT PATHWAYS	Italy
SLIDING DOORS: CHOICES THAT SHAPE THE FUTURE	Italy
L2 — T.E.L.A. Â: TALENT PINK, EMPOWERMENT AND AGILE WORK	Italy
INSPIRING WOMEN: BETWEEN DESIGN, ETHICS AND DIGITAL INNOVATION	Italy
L2 — PINK TEXTURE: A WEB OF SKILLS FOR WOMEN’S WORK	Italy
L4 — FRIDA	Italy
L4 — W@MEN ACT — WOMEN WHO ACT ON CHANGE	Italy
DIGITAL WOMEN: THE NEW ROLE OF FEMALE STAFF IN THE MARKETING AND DIGITAL SERVICES SECTOR	Italy
RECEPTIONIST	Italy
COMPUTER SCIENCE OF CITIZENSHIP	Italy
DIGITAL CUSTOMER	Italy
L2 — THE FUTURE OF WOMEN’S WORK: CHANGE, CHALLENGE, CHANCE	Italy
L4 — HYBRID JOB: PATHWAY FOR PROFESSIONAL CAREER DEVELOPMENT IN DIGITAL MARKETING	Italy
“L2 —”THE VALUE OF GENDER DIVERSITY IN THE COMPANY FOR WORKING ECOSYSTEMS “SMART”	Italy
R.E.P. CITIZENS OF THE DIGITAL WORLD... TECHNOLOGICALLY BULLISED	Italy
LINE 2 — LIFE AT WORK: AGILE WORK, SKILLS HYBRIDISATION, TRAINING AND EMPOWERMENT FOR WOMEN-FRIENDLY WORK	Italy
L2 — INCREASING DIGITAL MINDSET TO GOVERN PEOPLE AND PROCESSES IN MANUFACTURING	Italy

Initiative title	Country
L2 — TO BE BORN A WOMAN, TO BE BORN AGAIN: ORGANISATIONAL CHANGE AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION FOR COMPANIES AND PROFESSIONALS	Italy
GROWING A GAME	Italy
S.F.I.D.R.E	Italy
IP.AZ.A. (SCIENCE &S: HYPOTHESIS, ACTION, LEARNING)	Italy
L2 — WOMEN AT WORK- THE SUSTAINABLE WORK SITE	Italy
M.IN.D. — IMPROVEMENT, INTERNATIONALISATION AND DIGITALISATION	Italy
ENROSADIRA — FEMALE EMPOWERMENT ACTIONS IN THE WORLD OF WORK	Italy
IN VALUE: COURSES FOR WOMEN ON DIGITAL, LINGUISTIC AND PRE-PROFESSIONALISATION SKILLS (SETS: TOURISM, TRADE AND SECRETARIAL ADMINISTRATION)	Italy
LET’S ORIENT OURSELVES	Italy
L2 — WOMEN AND SMART TECHNOLOGY DIGITISATION CREATIVITY ORGANISATION	Italy
ACTIVITIES OF MUSEUMS BUILT INSIDE A TOWER BELONGING TO PRIVATE INDIVIDUALS, LOCATED IN THE STONE DISTRICTS.	Italy
L1 &WOMEN PIT STOP: TOOLS AND MODELS FOR WOMEN BACK TO RUNNING	Italy
DIGITAL ACCESSIBILITY E-INCLUSION: ACTIONS ON THE TERRITORY FOR WOMEN IMMIGRATION	Italy
L4-BUTTON UP: DIGITAL TISSUES AND TAILORS 4.0 TO WOMEN	Italy
JOB-HER. WOMEN ON THE MOVE	Italy
L1 _ WOMEN AND FUTURE BETWEEN TRAINING AND NARRATION	Italy
SECRETARIAL SUPPORT - Q1965019	Italy
L2 — DIGITAL AWARENESS AND SKILLS FOR WOMEN IN THE WORLD OF WORK	Italy
L2 — SKILL@TE IN PINK	Italy
W3 &WOMEN WORK WELFARE — CREATIVE, DIGITAL AND HYBRID SKILLS FOR CHANGING WORK	Italy
WOW — WOMEN ON SMART WORKING	Italy
Increase the company’s competitiveness through the implementation of innovation	Poland
Success is a woman!	Poland
Support for women over 29 years of age who are unemployed from the Silesian Voivodship in the process of professional activation.	Poland
With a computer for Mr. Brother	Poland
With an internship in the future	Poland
Professional activation of unemployed women aged 30 years and over in the Limanowski district	Poland
Lower Silesian Business Women	Poland
DLBC – Innovative Projects Experimental LAG Envolv20 Almada	Portugal
Creation of a new establishment of female entrepreneurship the area of restoration aimed at tourism and the public of regional base	Portugal
Project (Des)Involve Equality	Portugal

Initiative title	Country
ICT ADD — Digital Literacy and ICT Competitive Development for employees from enterprises operating in CNS sectors/SNCDI domains in South-West Oltenia and South-Muntenia Region	Romania
Increasing transparency, quality and accessibility of services provided to citizens by the judicial system, with the help of technology	Romania
Materials Business Center	Sweden
Increased digitalisation of startups in the field of sustainability and health.	Sweden
Pilot study Attraction Värmland	Sweden
Future Skills in Blekinge	Sweden
Gender Smart Arena	Sweden
The KULPosočje	Slovenia
Digital skills for a successful future	Slovakia